

Learning Behaviour of UG & PG Students of University College of Physical Education, Guru Kashi University Talwandi Sabo, Bhatinda (Punjab) During Lockdown Period

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study to examine the learning status of online classes of under graduate and post graduate student related to physical education department of Guru Kashi University Talwandi Sabo, Bhatinda (Punjab) during lockdown period. For this study an online survey was conducted to collect the data through Google form from 15 July 2021 to 25 July 2021. A self-structural questionnaire prepared in the Google form and sent to students through WhatsApp and E-mail. A total 230 students provide complete details. The percentage method was used to analysis the learning status of under graduate and post graduate students related to Physical Education courses during lockdown period. During the lock down period 80% students were actively participated in online learning or classes. Out of this percentage most students used mobile phone in online learning. Student facing many problems like stress, depression anxiety, poor internet facility, lack of study environment at home, lack of practical activity in physically manner. Students from rural area faced huge challenges during online classes. Finding of this study to create a positive space for online study of students related to physical education courses. Colleges and Universities make plan to develop an online education system for physical education related students.

Key Words- *E-learning, Sports, Physical Education, Behaviours, Lock Down*

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 is a disease caused by a new strain of corona virus. 'CO' stands for corona, 'VI' for virus, and 'D' for disease. Formerly, this disease was referred to as '2019 novel corona virus. Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory

syndrome corona virus. The virus is an enveloped RNA corona virus which is mainly transmitted from person-to-person respiratory spread, people who are in close contact with each other or respiratory droplets produced when an infected person coughs or sneezes and to a lesser extent from contact with contaminated surfaces or objects. It

was first identified in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and has since spread world level, resulting in on-going pandemic. As of 17 May 2020, more than 4.63 million cases have been reported across 188 countries and territories, resulting in more than 311,000 deaths. More than 1.69 million people have recovered as per WHO data. Many countries in the world are currently in some or other form of lockdown or restricted movement policy and practicing social distancing. In India all state governments have initiated several strategies to control the spread of the disease. Since 25 March, in India most state governments have observed lockdown, which is extended time to time. During lockdown closer of educational institute badly affected teaching learning system of educational institutions. All higher educational institutes directed to their teaching staff to take classes online.

RESULT

Table 1: Number of respondents according to gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	172	74.78
Female	58	25.22
Total	230	100

Table 1 illustrates the number and percentages of the respondents according to gender. This section reports the demographics of the sample. The study sample consisted of 230 participants. As can be seen there were number of respondents (74.78%

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This study was based on an online survey of 230 under graduate and post graduate student related to physical education courses of Guru Kashi University Talwandi Sabo (Punjab) during lockdown period. For this study an online survey was conducted to collect the data through Google form from 15 July 2021 to 25 July 2021. A self-structural questionnaire prepared in the Google form and sent to students through WhatsApp and E-mail. A total 230 students provide complete details. Descriptive statistics were carried out to understand the distribution of study participants. The percentage method was used to analysis the learning status, method of learning, problem faced by students, students’ opinion on different question related to online classes during lockdown period.

Male, 25.22% female). It is concluded that number of participations in physical education courses at graduation and post-graduation level male participates are greater than women.

Table 2: Number of respondents according to classes

Class	Frequency	Percentage
PG	86	37.39
UG	144	62.61
Total	230	100

Table 2 illustrates the number and percentages of the respondents according to class group. The study sample consisted of 230 participants. As can

be seen there were number of respondents (37.39% PG Students and 62.61% Under Graduate Students).

Table 3: Number of respondents according to living area

Ares	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	179	77.82
Urban	51	22.18
Total	230	100

Table 3 illustrates the number and percentages of the respondents according to living area. The study sample consisted of 230 participants. As can be seen there were number of respondents (77.82% belongs to rural area and 22.18% belongs to urban

or semi urban area). Seeing the figures of this table, we can say that the participation of people from rural environment in the field of sports and physical education is much higher than the urban area.

Table 4: Information about COVID-19

Statements with options	Frequency	Percentage	
When you heard first time about COVID-19	Jan-2020	103	44.78
	Feb-2020	53	23.04
	March-2020	74	32.18
What was the Source of information about COVID-19	social media	183	79.56
	Newspaper	13	05.65
	TV	34	14.79
Place of Residence during lockdown period	Home	218	94.78
	Other than home	12	05.22

Table number 4 shows the awareness of the students towards covid-19. 68 percent students came to know about covid-19 in January and February 2020 itself and about 80 percent got this information through social media. And during the

lockdown, 94 percent of the students were at their homes because they had already got information about covid-19. Data is showing that the most of students are aware about COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 5: Study status and academic atmosphere

Statements with options	Frequency	Percentage	
What was the mode of learning during lockdown	Online	163	70.88
	Online with textbook	51	22.17
	Textbook with self-efforts	16	06.95
Study room available separate at home	Yes	134	58.26
	No	96	41.74
How many Syllabuses covered	50%	87	37.82
	80%	89	38.69
	100%	54	23.48

Table 5 shows the data related to study status and academic atmosphere. Around 93 percent students adopted online study mode during the lockdown. About 58 percent of these students got a separate study room arrangement at home, the

rest either got a group space or had to study in an open space. About 62 percent believed that their syllabus was covered above 80 percent; the rest believed that their syllabus was covered more than 50 percent and less than 80 percent

Table 6: Online Class functioning

Statements with options	Frequency	Percentage	
Equipment available to attending online classes	Mobile	224	97.40
	Laptop	6	02.60
Past Experience attending online classes	Yes	77	33.48
	No	153	66.52
Arrangements of Mobile/Laptop	Friends	36	15.65
	Family	194	84.35
Study hour per day on online class	3 Hours	64	27.82
	4 Hours	61	26.52

	5 Hours	105	45.66
Attendance of Online Class in A week	Daily	110	47.83
	3 Day in Week	54	23.47
	5 Day in Week	66	28.70

Table 6 shows online Class functioning system. About 98 percent used mobile instead of laptop to attend online classes. About 67 percent also admitted that they had no prior experience of online classes, while the number of those with prior experience was close to 33 percent. 85

percent also said that their family had arranged for laptop or mobile. About 72 percent of the students attended online classes for 4 to 5 hours a day and about 77 percent of the students attended 5 days or more per week

Table 7: Influence of COVID-19 on Education and family

Statements with options		Frequency	Percentage
Do you think that low family income has affected your education?	Yes	200	86.96
	No	30	13.04
Do you think that the family economic condition affected by COVID 19.	Yes	220	95.65
	No	10	04.35
Problem facing during lockdown period.	Food	10	04.34
	Health	10	04.34
	Financial	100	43.48
	Study	110	47.84

Table 7 shows influence of COVID-19 on Education and family of students. About 87 percent of the students said that low family income had affected their education. 96 percent of the students

admitted that their family's financial condition has been affected due to covid-19. About 91 percent also told that they had to face study and economic problems during covid-19

Table 8: University role during online study

Statements with options		Frequency	Percentage
Does university provide any app or help for online study	Yes	204	88.70
	No	26	11.30

Does university teaching staffs provide any support	Yes	226	98.26
	No	4	01.74
Are you satisfied from online theory classes of Physical Education	Yes	172	74.78
	No	58	25.22
Are you satisfied from online Practical classes of Physical Education	Yes	134	58.26
	No	96	41.74
Do your teaching staffs encourage you to regarding online study	Yes	211	91.74
	No	19	08.26
After each class, your teaching staffs help you in understanding ways to improve your study	Yes	210	91.30
	No	20	08.70
Are you satisfied with the technology and software provided by university for online study	Yes	192	83.48
	No	38	16.52

Table 8 shows the data about behaviour of university administration and teaching staff during online study. About 89 percent of the students said that the university management made arrangements for online study. 97 percent also said that the university teaching staff provided full support for the study. 75 percent of the students agreed with the online study system of physical education theory classes. 59 percent students agreed with the online study system of physical

education practical classes, while the number of those who disagreed was also around 42 percent. Almost 92 percent of the students believe that the teaching staff boosted their morale towards online education, which inspired them to study online. 92 percent of the students said that after every class, the teaching staff gave advice and guidance to improve the study. 84 percent students praised the tools used by the university management for online education.

Table 9: Problem faced during online study

Statements with options	Frequency	Percentage	
Feeling of stress, depression, and anxieties due to online classes	Yes	70	30.44
	No	80	34.78
	Some times	80	34.78
Faced Internet problem	Yes	212	92.17
	No	18	07.83
Favourable Environment of Study at home	Yes	92	40
	No	138	60.00
In future which type of study you preferred	Online	50	21.74

Offline	180	78.26
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Table 9 data shows about problem faced by students during online study. About 65 percent of the students believe that they felt stress, depression and anxieties during the online study during the lock down. About 92 percent faced

internet problem. About 60 percent did not find a suitable environment for study at home. For this reason, 78 students have suggested offline study instead of online in future.

Table 10: Thinking about exam and result system

Statements with options	Frequency	Percentage
Have you face any problem during online exam	Yes	40
	No	190
Are you satisfied with university online exam system	Yes	185
	No	45
Is any training provided by your university staff to take exam online	Yes	202
	Not Required	28
In future which type of exam you preferred	Online	156
	Offline	74

Table 10 shows students thinking about exam and result system of university administration. About 83 percent of the students admitted that they did not face any problem during the online exam. 81 percent students were satisfied with the online examination system of the university. About 88

percent also said that they were also trained by the university administration on online exams, while 12 percent did not feel the need for training because they were familiar in such tasks. 68 percent students have a desire to conduct online exams in future also.

CONCLUSION

After looking at the entire result, it is concluded that on an average the participation of men in undergraduate and postgraduate courses of physical education is much higher than that of women. The second important thing also emerged

that the participation of students from rural environment in the field of physical education and sports is 78 percent, which also proves that the passion for sports is in the villages and not in the cities. One thing has emerged that the students

were very aware of covid-19 and due to this, maximum students had reached their homes during the lock down. About 92 percent of the students used online study and the syllabus of almost all the students was also covered from 50 percent to 100 percent but almost half of the students at home could not get a separate study room for online study. Students also participated enthusiastically in online classes and 98 percent used mobile for online classes. Close to 90 percent of the students also believed that due to the lock down, their studies, the financial condition of the family were greatly affected, due to which they also had to face financial problems. More than 90 percent of the students believe that for online study, the teachers of the university administration and department helped wholeheartedly and removed all kinds of problems. About 65 percent also felt some stress etc. The problem of internet mainly for the students and lack of environment for proper study at home was also there. For this reason, about 79 percent have placed a demand for offline classes in future. The experience of the students regarding the online exam and results was very good. More than 90 percent students have praised the online examination system of the university. On one hand students are demanding offline classes and on the other hand they want exams in online mode. Thus, it can be said that during online education, especially the students associated with physical education and sports have to face a lot of problems in practical classes. Apart from this, rural background and family economic

condition has also been the main problem somewhere. Nevertheless, with the support of the University Administration and the teaching staff of the University College of Physical Education, students can easily participate in the online education process.

RECOMNDATION

As a recommendation, it can be said that online education is not very beneficial especially for physical education and sports courses. Because the field of physical education and sports is completely connected with the field, in other words we can say that practical classes hold a very important role in this field. If still, online classes have to be run in the event of disaster or pandemic, then along with prior training to the students, provision of laptop and internet facility etc. should be arranged by the government free of cost or interest-free loan by the university administration. If there is such a system, then the student can take education without any stress and pressure.

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